

A Hybrid Spiking-Convolutional Neural Network Approach for Advancing High-Quality Image Inpainting

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1. Introduction

Traditional image inpainting methods use computer vision and image processing to restore missing or corrupted picture portions [19, 4]. The technique involves identifying damaged areas, which is sometimes aided by masks, and using inpainting algorithms to build precise approximations of the original image [2, 21, 16]. Although there are other techniques, such as patch-based, texture synthesis, and diffusion-based methods, they may struggle with picture semantics and capturing subtle details. Machine learning approaches, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), show potential in image inpainting by effectively learning and utilizing high-level characteristics and spatial dependencies [20, 17, 10]. However, CNNs may encounter difficulties in capturing temporal dynamics and intricate spatial relationships [6, 18, 7].

To overcome these limitations, this study provides a unique hybrid approach to image inpainting that combines Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) with CNNs. SNNs, which are inspired by the brain's spiking neurons, differ from typical neural networks in that they represent neural activity as discrete spikes across time, capturing temporal information in a biologically realistic manner [5, 13, 12]. This unique encoding enables SNNs to understand intricate temporal patterns within image data. Meanwhile, CNNs, recognized for their effectiveness in image processing, excel in extracting meaningful features through convolutional layers, adeptly capturing spatial patterns and local dependencies [3].

Furthermore, in the proposed SC-NN hybrid for image inpainting, a customized dataset was employed for training and testing, specifically designed for inpainting tasks. By

introducing missing regions, this dataset replicates various inpainting circumstances such as occlusions or intentional object removal. During training and validation, the hybrid model is fine-tuned using a mean squared error (MSE) loss function, which measures differences between generated inpainted regions and the ground truth in non-corrupted parts. A validation loss of 0.0017 demonstrates the model's capacity for unseen data, while a training loss of 0.015 suggests accurate learning and adaptation. This hybrid model excels in producing precise and visually appealing inpainted images by combining SNNs and CNNs, presenting a promising solution for image inpainting problems.

2. Proposed Hybrid Approach

In our proposed architecture, we use the SNN model to capture temporal dynamics and contextual information in the image [8, 14]. Simultaneously, CNNs are used for feature extraction to fill in missing or corrupted regions. SNNConv2d layers are introduced in the model, which integrates spiking neuron principles [9] into convolutional layers. This inclusion allows the model to extract spatial, temporal, and contextual information from the input image. Combining this temporal information with spatial variables derived from typical CNN layers allows SNNs and CNNs to work together to their full potential. SNNConv2d layers differ from traditional convolutional layers in that they use spike-based activation functions rather than fundamental ones like ReLU or sigmoid. These functions produce spikes that signify neuron activation and encode temporal data.

2.1. Hybrid SC-NN Model

The SC-NN model integrates SNNs and CNNs, utilizing their respective strengths to create a robust, biologically inspired architecture for handling intricate inpainting

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tasks. This fusion captures both local and temporal aspects of visual data, promising improved performance and efficiency in tasks like image inpainting. To add spiking behavior into convolutional operations, the SC-NN hybrid model combines SNN layers with CNN layers. Firstly, the SNN component processes the input image by simulating neural spikes to extract temporal information and encode the temporal context, including available regions. This encoded temporal information is subsequently used by the CNN component, which uses spatial processing along with the available picture areas to construct inpainted regions. As a result, the SC-NN architecture takes advantage of the complementary strengths of SNN for capturing temporal dynamics and CNN for spatial processing to improve its performance in image inpainting tasks.

Six layers are used in the hybrid model, including SNNConv2d and conventional CNNConv2d layers. Five CNNConv2d layers perform typical convolutional functions, while one SNNConv2d layer adds spiking activity. Following that, ReLU activation functions improve feature-capture capabilities. The gradual increase of output channels per layer captures fine details. CNN layers extract relevant features using filters and activation functions. The SNNConv2d layer performs spiking neural network convolutional operations in the absence of explicit equations. The inpainted image with three RGB channels is produced by the final CNN Conv2d layer. With six layers, including SNNConv2d and CNN Conv2d, it successfully blends spiking neural processing and traditional convolutional operations, making it well-suited for image inpainting tasks by capturing both spatial and temporal information.

2.1.1 LIF Neural Model

SNN uses the Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) neural model [15], a commonly used model for mimicking SNN dynamics, in the proposed architecture. The LIF model’s basic structure involves computing the membrane potential, generating spikes upon threshold crossing (similar to genetic logic circuits [11]), resetting the potential, and outputting output. $V(t)$ reflects the electrical potential difference across the neuron’s cell membrane as impacted by incoming input signals and a leakage factor. Equation 1 is used to estimate the membrane potential dynamics in the constructed LIF model.

$$\frac{dV(t)}{dt} = \frac{I(t) - \frac{V(t)}{R}}{C} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Dataset

The proposed architecture introduces a novel image inpainting approach based on a customized dataset. This dataset is designed for SC-NN model training, generating masks with intentionally missing regions to serve as ground

truth for inpainting. It includes diverse inpainting scenarios such as occlusions and object removal, allowing the model to learn a variety of strategies. Shuffling and partitioning the dataset into 80% for training and 20% for validation and testing is used to preprocess it. The LSDIR Dataset [1], which is well-known for its appropriateness in image restoration, is used to achieve cutting-edge performance in picture inpainting.

3. Conclusion

This paper presents a hybrid SC-NN architecture for effective image inpainting, combining SNNs and CNNs. The model, which includes SNNConv2d layers, outperforms state-of-the-art approaches by decreasing reconstruction mistakes with lower loss values. The effectiveness indicates a wide range of applications in image regeneration assignments. Combining SNNConv2d with regular CNN layers takes advantage of both SNN and CNN strengths. Future plans include refining the model, investigating applications, and solving real-world problems. The findings highlight SNN’s potential for enhancing artificial intelligence.

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5. Footnotes

All of the experiments have been performed using a proposed hybrid SC-NN model. The source code is available publically at ¹.

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¹Github - <https://github.com/Rao-Sanaullah/A-Hybrid-SC-NN-Approach/tree/main>

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